

Solid angle subtended by a regular n-gonal right pyramid (solid or hollow) at its apex

Harish Chandra Rajpoot

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, New Delhi 110016, India

Introduction: In this paper, the analytic formula has been derived for finding out the solid angle subtended by a regular n-gonal right pyramid at its apex by using the formula of solid angle subtended by a regular n-polygonal plane at any point lying on the perpendicular passing through its centre, which has already been derived in HCR's Theory of Polygon [1,2]. The solid angle subtended by a regular n-gonal right pyramid will be derived in terms of apex angle α i.e. angle between any two consecutive lateral edges meeting at the apex [3] & the number n of sides in regular polygonal base of the right pyramid.

Derivation: Let there be a right pyramid (solid or hollow) with normal height 'H', apex point 'P', angle between any two consecutive lateral edges ' α ' & base as a regular polygon with 'n' no. of the sides each of length 'a' (as shown in Figure 1, the upper part shows the isometric front view & lower one the top view)

Now, join centre 'O' of the base to all the vertices $A_1, A_2, A_3 \dots \dots A_n$ of the regular polygonal base to obtain n number of congruent isosceles triangles (as shown in Figure 1).

Consider an isosceles $\Delta A_1 O A_2$ & drop the perpendicular OM to the mid-point 'M' of side $A_1 A_2$ of regular polygonal base to obtain two congruent right triangles $\Delta A_1 M O$ & $\Delta A_2 M O$.

In right $\Delta A_1 M O$ (see polygonal base of pyramid in Fig. 1),

$$\tan \angle A_1 O M = \frac{A_1 M}{O M}$$

$$\tan \frac{\pi}{n} = \frac{\left(\frac{a}{2}\right)}{O M}$$

$$O M = \frac{a}{2} \cot \frac{\pi}{n}$$

In right $\Delta P M A_1$ (see upper part in above Fig.1),

$$\tan \angle A_1 P M = \frac{A_1 M}{P M}$$

$$\tan \frac{\alpha}{2} = \frac{\left(\frac{a}{2}\right)}{P M}$$

$$P M = \frac{a}{2} \cot \frac{\alpha}{2}$$

Figure 1: A perpendicular PM is dropped from apex P to the mid-point M of side $A_1 A_2$ of base of regular n-gonal right pyramid to obtain a right $\Delta P M A_1$

By joining the point 'P' to the centre 'O' and the point 'M', we obtain a right ΔPOM (as shown in Figure 2)

In right ΔPOM ,

$$PM^2 = OP^2 + OM^2$$

$$\left(\frac{a}{2} \cot \frac{\alpha}{2}\right)^2 = H^2 + \left(\frac{a}{2} \cot \frac{\pi}{n}\right)^2$$

$$H^2 = \frac{a^2}{4} \left(\cot^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n} \right)$$

$$H = \frac{a}{2} \sqrt{\cot^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}$$

Figure 2: $PO = H$ is the normal height of n-gonal right pyramid.

Above is the general formula to compute the normal height of a regular n-gonal right pyramid when apex angle α , number of sides n & length of each side a of regular polygonal base are known.

The solid angle ($\omega_{pyramid}$) subtended by the regular n-gonal right pyramid at its apex P will be equal to the solid angle ($\omega_{polygon}$) subtended by regular n-gon $A_1A_2A_3 \dots A_n$ of each side a , at the apex P lying a normal height H from the centre 'O' which is given by the formula of HCR's Theory of Polygon [1, 2] as follows

$$\omega_{polygon} = 2\pi - 2n \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{2H \sin \frac{\pi}{n}}{\sqrt{4H^2 + a^2 \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}} \right) \quad \forall (n \in N \text{ \& } n \geq 3)$$

Now, setting the value of H in the above general formula of solid angle, we get the solid angle subtended by the regular n-gonal right pyramid at its apex as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_{pyramid} &= 2\pi - 2n \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{2 \left(\frac{a}{2} \sqrt{\cot^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}} \right) \sin \frac{\pi}{n}}{\sqrt{4 \left(\frac{a}{2} \sqrt{\cot^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}} \right)^2 + a^2 \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}} \right) \\ &= 2\pi - 2n \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{a \sin \frac{\pi}{n} \sqrt{\cot^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}}{\sqrt{a^2 \cot^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - a^2 \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n} + a^2 \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}} \right) \\ &= 2\pi - 2n \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{a \sin \frac{\pi}{n} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\tan^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}} - \frac{1}{\tan^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}}}{a \cot \frac{\alpha}{2}} \right) \\ &= 2\pi - 2n \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{a \sin \frac{\pi}{n} \sqrt{\tan^2 \frac{\pi}{n} - \tan^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}}{a \cot \frac{\alpha}{2} \tan \frac{\alpha}{2} \tan \frac{\pi}{n}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$= 2\pi - 2n\sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sin \frac{\pi}{n} \sqrt{\tan^2 \frac{\pi}{n} - \tan^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}}{\left(\frac{\sin \frac{\pi}{n}}{\cos \frac{\pi}{n}} \right)} \right)$$

$$= 2\pi - 2n\sin^{-1} \left(\cos \frac{\pi}{n} \sqrt{\tan^2 \frac{\pi}{n} - \tan^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}} \right)$$

Hence, the **solid angle (ω) subtended at the apex by any right pyramid with normal height H , base as a regular polygon with n number of sides each of length a and the apex angle α (i.e. angle between any two consecutive lateral edges), is given by the following formula**

$$\omega = 2\pi - 2n\sin^{-1} \left(\frac{2H\sin \frac{\pi}{n}}{\sqrt{4H^2 + a^2 \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}} \right) = 2\pi - 2n\sin^{-1} \left(\cos \frac{\pi}{n} \sqrt{\tan^2 \frac{\pi}{n} - \tan^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}} \right)$$

$$\text{Where, } n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 3 \text{ \& } 0 \leq \alpha \leq \frac{2\pi}{n}$$

And the relation among the apex angle ' α ', side of regular n-gonal base a & normal height ' H ' of the right pyramid, is given by the above equation (as highlighted in green colour above) as follows

$$H = \frac{a}{2} \sqrt{\cot^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}$$

Thus, any of above formula can be used to compute the solid angle subtended by a regular n-gonal right pyramid at its vertex when

- 1) H = normal height, a = length of each side & n = number of sides of regular polygonal base are known or
- 2) α = apex angle & n = number of sides of regular polygonal base of right pyramid are known.

Note: Above articles had been *derived & illustrated* by **Mr H.C. Rajpoot (M Tech, Production Engineering)**

Indian Institute of Technology Delhi

22 July, 2019

Email: hcrajpoot.iitd@gmail.com

Author's Home Page: <https://notionpress.com/author/HarishChandraRajpoot>

References

- [1] Rajpoot HC. HCR's Theory of Polygon (proposed by harish chandra rajpoot) solid angle subtended by any polygonal plane at any point in the space. Int. J. Math. Phys. Sci. Res. 2014;2:28-56. [Google Scholar](#)
- [2] Rajpoot HC. HCR's Theory of Polygon. Solid angle subtended by any polygonal plane at any point in the space. 2019. [Google Scholar](#)
- [3] Rajpoot HC. Mathematical analysis of a tetrahedron: dihedral angles between consecutive faces and solid angle at a vertex given the face angles. ResearchGate; 2015 Mar. doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.34440.23042